

NEW TECHNOLOGIES AND APPROACHES TO TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

The given article is dedicated to the study of active learning approaches as an effective method in teaching foreign languages. There is a classification of two main principles for organizing brainstorming processes. The first principle is that collective work produces ideas of higher quality. Moreover, an individual approach to the same idea may lead to its rejection due to insufficient justification. If the same idea is presented to the group, it can be further developed, supplemented and improved by other participants.

Key words: student involvement, learning process, direct, interaction, foreign language.

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There are currently a large number of different technologies and approaches to teaching foreign languages. Some methods are already being used in educational institutions, while others are still at the stage of implementation and testing before becoming part of the educational process.

Modern students show changing interests, so the task of involving students in lessons and influencing their perception to achieve better results becomes especially relevant [2]. Foreign languages seem difficult for many students, and since these languages are not their native languages, teachers of English and other foreign languages need to use effective teaching methods in their practice.

In this article, we analyze the basic concepts and principles of active language learning. What do active learning methods include? These methods are a set of pedagogical actions and techniques that are aimed at organizing the learning process and creating various conditions that stimulate students to independently and creatively master the educational material during cognitive activity.

It is known that the role of the teacher has been transformed from an informant into the role of an expert organizing information interaction.

The concept of active learning is not new in pedagogy. The founders of these methods are considered to be such famous teachers as J. A. Komensky, I. G. Pestalozzi, F. A. V. Diesterweg, G. W. F. Hegel, J. Rousseau and D. Dewey.

Learning foreign languages is more than just working with dictionaries. The authoritative linguist and developer of foreign language teaching methods

E. P. Shubin, in his book “Basic Principles of Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages” emphasizes that it is necessary to master not only the general principles of the methodology, but also to know what the specific aspects of teaching are [5]. Active learning methods allow you to combine your native and foreign languages, which contribute to better adaptation and perception.

Let us consider the positive results of using presentations in foreign language lessons as an example, since they are one of the methods of active learning. Using computer presentations in the educational process allows conducting classes on a completely new level, projecting slides from the computer screen onto a large screen. A multimedia presentation is

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a huge material for communication in a foreign language and is the basis for a monologue, providing a wonderful opportunity to implement the communicative function of the language. With the help of presentations, listening, visual perception and much more are possible [3].

The brainstorming method also refers to active learning methods. The basis of this method is the pedagogical cooperation of participants and the discussion component, which helps participants to release their creative potential and overcome semantic and moral barriers. This method allows all group members to think openly and freely. The manifestation of creative potential becomes an important element that allows developing ideas for creative participation in the brainstorming process [1].

If we turn to historical aspects, we will note that the concept of brainstorming arose in the distant past. In particular, this idea was used by the Vikings to make the only correct and practically applicable decision that required an unconventional approach to resolving a difficult situation. Thus, in the times of the Vikings, a collective council was held on the ship, at which all members of the crew offered their ideas, after which the captain chose one of the proposals.

Let's move on to the issues of organizing brainstorming, which A.F. Osborn described in his 1953 book, entitled "Guided Imagination" - brainstorming .

Brainstorming is a purposeful method of solving complex problems through collective discussion, focused on a creative and original solution, based on the opinion of one of the interviewed participants.

In addition, this theory is patented and is actively used in modern pedagogical technologies. This method may be characterized by spontaneity and subjectivity, but it is successfully applied in practice, since it involves the entire group and is aimed at solving current problems.

There is a classification of two main principles for organizing brainstorming processes. The first principle is that collective work produces ideas of higher quality. Moreover, an individual approach to the same idea may lead to its rejection due to insufficient justification. If the same idea is presented to the group, it can be further developed, supplemented and improved by other participants.

The second principle is that participants in a discussion, when generating ideas, evaluate the situation more critically. At the same time, it is much easier to criticize the opinion of one participant than the opinion of a group of like-minded people.

Numerous educational possibilities of the game method are known. The effectiveness of using game methods has been recognized by many researchers involved in the methodology of teaching foreign languages. This is explained by the fact that during the game the abilities of any person, especially a child, are revealed to the fullest and sometimes unexpectedly. There are many definitions of the game. As Stronina M.F. states, "the game is a type of activity in situations aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which self-management of behavior is formed and improved" [4].

A game is a form of social practice, an active reproduction of life phenomena outside of a real practical setting. It always exists in two time dimensions: the present and the future, providing immediate pleasure, as well as satisfaction of current personal needs. In a game, life situations are modeled and characteristics, qualities, states, skills and abilities necessary for the performance of social, professional and creative tasks are consolidated.

A.V. Konyshcheva identifies the following functions of play activity:

- 1) entertaining (awakening interest);
- 2) communicative (mastering the dialectic of communication);
- 3) diagnostic (identification of deviations from standard behavior, self-knowledge in the process of the game);
- 4) play therapy (overcoming various difficulties that arise in other aspects of life).

Thus, based on the above, we can conclude that active teaching methods are the most effective and productive in the process of early teaching of foreign languages to children.

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